

TYPES OF POLLINATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE FOR THE ENVIRONMENT.

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the types of pollination and its importance for the environment.

Pollination This is the process of transferring pollen from the "male" part of the flower to the female part. Its purpose is to fertilize the ovule (present in the female gametophyte), the pollen grains that represent the male gametophyte. , can self-pollinate), the sexual reproduction of plants is highly dependent on this process. the material mixes to form a seed that leads to the birth of a new plant, possibly with traits from both parents Responsible for the production and protection of sex cells (female and male gametophytes) The reproductive organ of angiosperms (flowering plants) is the flower, where pollination takes place. There are several types of pollination, and some of them are biotic (animal) or ab It is different from the pollinator, which can be biotic (wind, water). Biotic pollination is very dependent on the characteristics of the flower, as it is usually used for feeding, sheltering,

breeding, etc. It attracts some unique features.[1]

process,

Pollination is the transfer of pollen grains from the male part of one flower to the female part of another (or in the case of self-pollination) and depends on external agents known as pollinators.

- How does pollination happen?

When a pollen grain reaches the level of the stigma, it "germinates" and forms a long structure called a pollen tube. The pollen tube grows downward through the style, that is, in the direction of the ovary. Many recognition and signaling mechanisms are involved in the growth of the pollen tube toward the ovary, and as in many animals , all the pollen tubes that germinate and grow do not reach the ovary and move forward. fertilization. When the pollen tube enters the female gametophyte (ovule), the sperm cell located in the pollen grain fertilizes the egg cell. Soon, due to the

process of fertilization and after the fusion of the nuclei of the two cells, a zygote is formed. This zygote, as it develops in the embryo, becomes the most important dispersal organ of plants with later sexual reproduction. In addition to the sperm cell that achieves the fertilization of the oocell, another sperm cell located in the same pollen grain unites with two or more nuclei from the female gametophyte; this process is known as double fertilization. The aforementioned fusion forms a "polyploid endospermic nucleus" which is responsible for the production of the endosperm (food material) from which the seed develops during embryo development and germination. Pollination can be classified as "self-pollination" and "cross-pollination" or "biotic" and "abiotic" depending on where the pollen grains come from. [2]

- self pollination

There are species of plants with female and male flowers on the same stem, but there are also those with bisexual flowers, that is, they have male and female gametophytes (androecium and gynoecium) at the same time and in the same flower) there is.).

Some authors consider pollination between same-sex flowers of the same plant to be "interfloral pollination", while what happens between reproductive structures of the same flower is "intrafloral pollination". Although it allows for the reproduction of self-pollinated individuals, self-pollination means that the mating gametes are genetically identical, so that the plants produced from the resulting seeds are identical to the parent o plants have their own "clones".[3]

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cross pollination

In contrast to the process of self-pollination, cross-pollination involves the

exchange of pollen between flowers of different plants (unisexual or bisexual). In other words, this process involves the transfer of a pollen grain from the anther of one flower to the stigma of another, another plant. Since the genetic material exchanged during cross-pollination comes from genetically different parents, the seed The seeds produced after the germination process give rise to genetically and phenotypically different plants.

- Biotic and abiotic pollination;

Depending on the vector that mediates the transfer of the pollen grain from the anthers of one flower to the stigma of another (or the same), pollination can be classified as biotic or abiotic.

Biotic pollination;

This type of pollination is perhaps the most representative and important of all. It involves the participation of an animal, usually an insect, in the movement of pollen grains from one place to another. Although more than 50% of pollination is carried out by various insects and arthropods, vertebrates such as birds and bats play an important role in this process. plays

The plant world is full of surprises and wonders. The evolution of plants to adapt and reproduce is truly amazing. This is manifested by different types of pollination, through which plants survive and carry out their own reproduction. Obviously, this is a very interesting topic. Later we will think more about the process of pollination. We explain how it is produced and its importance not only to the plant kingdom, but to the entire planet. In addition, we will talk about the different types of pollination available. If you are interested in this topic, I recommend that you continue reading. Before talking about

the different types of pollination available, we will explain what exactly this process is. Well, pollination of plants is basically a biological process in which the pollen produced by the male structures of the plants are transferred to the female parts. If this plant has both male and female organs and/or flowers, they can be found within the same plant. But pollination also takes place between different plants, which have only male or female flowers. I think that in the last case this process is called cross-pollination. It should be said that this interesting process is the first stage of plant reproduction. Thus, we can confirm that the main task of pollination is clearly the first step to ensure the survival and development of plants due to reproduction. If you want to know more about this topic, I recommend that you take a look at this article on the topic of what is plant fertilization.

How does the pollination of plants happen? As we mentioned above, the whole process of pollination is necessary for the fertilization of plants. without them reproduction was impossible. However, we will consider in more detail what exactly this process consists of. In natural pollination, pollen transport is carried out by abiotic and biotic agents. These ensure that the male gametes, i.e. the pollen grains originally located in the stamen of the flower, fertilize the female gametes or ovules in the pistil of the flower. These are developed both by the plants themselves and by pollinators. An excellent example of the pollination process carried out by insects is the wonderful phenomenon *Ophrys bombyliflora*, known as the bumblebee orchid. Their color and texture are very similar to the female body of some bumblebee species, hence their name. Due

to this similarity, this flower can attract male bees. It sits atop a flower and fills its hairy body with pollen, which it eventually carries to other orchids. And this is how this type of plant grows.

What are the 4 types of pollination?

The plant world is full of amazing processes and strategies. A good example is the different types of pollination available, which we will discuss in this section. We can distinguish this process by the way it is implemented. This would be the following classification:

Wind Pollination: It is done by wind.

Hydrophilic Pollination: It takes place through water.

Zoophilic pollination: This is done by animals.

In this last group, zoophilic pollination, a specific subgroup is distinguished, which may be the most famous: entomophilous pollination, which is carried out by insects. There are thousands of insects that participate in the pollination process of millions of different plants found in countless ecosystems on our planet. In addition to this classification, we can distinguish four main types of pollination, which we explain below:

crusade,

Straight away,

naturally

artificial,

Cross pollination

,Let's start with cross-pollination. What is this guy? How is this done? Well, in this type of pollination, pollen grains are transferred from the flower of one plant to the flower of another. That is why it is called "crusade". Pollen is transferred from one plant to another by a means called an external vector. It can be both abiotic and biotic. Cross-pollination occurs when birds

such as hummingbirds or bats participate in the process; insects such as bees, wasps and butterflies; wind or water. In this large group we can include all the types that we described earlier: anemophilic pollination, hydrophilic pollination and zoophilic pollination. even when it appears at different times during the period. Some examples of these can be almonds, melons and sunflowers. But there are many more species that need cross-pollination to reproduce.

Direct pollination;

Among the four main types of pollination, direct pollination is also distinguished, which is also called self-fertilization or self-pollination. In such cases, pollen is transferred from the anthers of the flower to the stigmas of the flower. The most remarkable thing about this process is that the pollen grain only travels from one point to another without an intermediary vector, as in cross-pollination.

Plant species that perform direct pollination or self-pollination are called autogamous. A big advantage of this type of pollination is that plant species are able to reproduce without external pollinators. It should also be noted that almost no pollen is wasted in this way, since the distances traveled by the grains are usually very short. Autogamous plants include, for example, beans, mangoes, peanuts and peas.

Natural pollination;

Now let's talk about natural pollination. As expected, this happens without human intervention, that is, naturally. All situations involving direct pollination, including anemophilic, hydrophilic, and entomophilous types of pollination, are examples of natural pollination. completely naturally and without the help of people

found a way to transport to meet some specific needs, to be able to reproduce. All the types of pollination we have discussed so far occur naturally, without our intervention.

Artificial pollination;

In contrast to natural pollination, there is artificial pollination, which is also called manual pollination. As you can imagine, this process takes place with human intervention. In fact, this happens when we change the nature during the process and control the reproduction of plants. Usually, this process is carried out manually for two reasons:

when there are very few natural pollinators in a given area where agricultural crops are located.

When we want to prevent the change of specific characteristics of a certain plant.

But how is this done? A large number of simple, but hardworking. It is important to bag the flowers to prevent the arrival of natural pollinators. We need to collect the pollen from the stamen and transfer them to the stigma. For this, we can use, for example, a brush. Then you need to cover the flowers again until they are fertilized.

The importance of pollination;

With all this information, it is already clear what pollination is and its importance to the plant kingdom. However, this process is vital not only for plants, but also for us. Thanks to them, the balance of ecosystems is ensured, as well as food security for people. We must not forget that agricultural production directly depends on the pollination of crops. Without pollination, new individuals of the plant will not appear. Without new plants, we and the herbivores would lack food. As a result of the extinction of herbivores, carnivores are also negatively affected. It

should also be noted that high biodiversity of pollinators contributes to the balance of both natural ecosystems and crops. Thus, resilience in natural and agricultural ecosystems can be fostered through the biodiversity of their pollinators. Their ecological function and response to environmental conditions can minimize the risks caused by climate change. This detail is very important, because this problem poses a strong threat to current and future ecosystems. As you can see, pollination is necessary not only for plants, but also for the entire planet. Therefore, we must care for and respect ecosystems.[4]

Conclusion:

Pollination is a crucial process in the life cycle of many angiosperms. Without pollination, there is no fertilization and without the latter, no seeds are formed, pollination is important not only for plants, but also for the many animals that feed on them. The process itself preserves the genetic variability of plant species. It is important for the emergence of mechanisms of adaptation to various environmental factors, such as climate change, the presence of pathogens, etc. It is also an important process for the production of world agricultural products from an anthropocentric point of view.

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